

**Precision Agriculture
Association New Zealand**
TECHNOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

PA17 - The International Tri-Conference for Precision Agriculture in 2017

- 7th Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Agriculture
- 1st Asian-Australasian Conference on Precision Pastures and Livestock Farming
- Digital Farmer and Grower 2017

Monday 16 - Wednesday 18 October 2017

CLAUDELANDS CONFERENCE AND
EXHIBITION CENTRE, HAMILTON

Farmers and growers practising the digital future

Proceedings of the *Digital Farmer and Grower 2017*

16 – 18 October 2017, Hamilton, New Zealand

Warrick Nelson (Editor) – The New Zealand Institute for Plant and Food Research Ltd

Lorraine McKenzie (Editorial support) – The New Zealand Institute for Plant and Food Research Ltd

Scientific Programme Committee

Craige MacKenzie (Chairman DGF)
Jim Grennell
Matt Flowerday
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Robyn Dynes
Ian Yule
Armin Werner (Chairman PA17)

Greenvale Pastures
Precision Agriculture Association NZ Inc
GPS-IT
Tru-Test Group
Landwise
AgResearch
Massey University
Lincoln Agritech Ltd

The *Digital Farmer and Grower 2017* was a conference of PA17 – The International Tri-Conference for Precision Agriculture in 2017

Tri-Conference combined organising committee members

Armin Werner - Conference Chairman
Jim Grennell – Chairman, PA17 Organising Committee
Craige Mackenzie – Chairman PAANZ
Mike Manning
Brendan O'Connell
Robyn Dynes
Carolyn Hedley
Anna Heslop
Ian Yule

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Precision Agriculture Association NZ Inc. (PAANZ)
Greenvale Pastures
Ravensdown Co-op
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AgResearch
Landcare Research
Foundation For Arable Research
Massey University

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1006674>

KEYNOTES/PLENARY

IOF2020: Fostering business and software ecosystems for large-scale uptake of IoT in food and farming

Cor Verdouw, Sjaak Wolfert*, George Beers, Harald Sundmaeker, Grigoris Chatzikostas
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1002903>

Future of farming: digital agronomy & analytics

Raj Khosla
DOI:

Fate and future of optical sensing in PA

Nicolas Tremblay*, Kosal Kuhn, Philippe Vigneault
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1002905>

Precision agriculture: global strategy in R&D for an enabling technology

Ian Ferguson
DOI:

Open data for agriculture and rural communities

Karel Charvát
DOI:

A new ag-sustainability model? Maori business culture!

Miriana Stephens
DOI:

PAPERS

Presentation

Farm management, benchmarking and purchase through satellite remote sensing – How can this work in the land of the Long White Cloud?

Brad Wooldridge,
Warialda, Western Australia, Australia
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7039473>

20 Years of PA on Branson Farms – the journey and economics

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<https://zenodo.org/10.5281/zenodo.7039866>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1006674>